

THE ROLE OF MILITARY-LEGAL ISSUES IN TIMUR'S REGULATIONS

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Temur tuzuklarda harbiy-huquqiy masalalarning o‘rni, Temur va Temuriylar davrida davlat va huquq masalalari va madaniyatining rivoji to‘g‘risida fikr va mulohazalar yoritilib o‘tilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: madaniyat, davlat, huquq, davr, qo‘shin, aql-farosat, buyuk jasorat, harbiy iste’dod, tiklash.

Аннотация. В данной статье освещается роль военно-правовых вопросов в эпоху правления Тимура и Тимуридов., а также размышления о вопросах государства и права, развитии культуры.

Ключевые слова: культура, государство, право, эпоха, армия, проницательность, великое мужество, военный талант, реставрация.

Annotation. This article highlights the role of military and legal issues during the reign of Timur and the Timurids, as well as reflections on issues of state and law, and the development of culture.

Keywords: culture, state, law, epoch, army, insight, great courage, military talent, restoration.

Along with famous scientists and statesmen, the past of the Uzbek people is decorated by such famous major military leaders as Mahmud Ghaznavi, Satuk Bugrokhan, Jalaliddin Manguberdiyev, Amir Temur, Babur, Sheibani Khan, Ubaidullahan the first, Abdullahan the second. But military-legal issues in the states where these commanders operated, one can say, have been little studied, with the exception of the period of Amir Temur. Military campaigns during the time of Amir Temur, as well as military law, attracted the attention of scientists in this field, and some scientific papers have been written about it. [1]

Since the state of Amir Temur was a military noble state based on medieval sole rule, the main part of the “Code” was devoted to military law, and these same issues in the work attracted the attention of scientists. Timur's kingdom finally had a huge army and a supply system.

Timur himself was considered the Supreme commander-in-chief, and during his absence, Amir ul-Umar was the Vice commander-in-chief for military affairs. The “Regulations” indicate that five people received this title: the ruler of Badakhshan, Amir Khudoyd, the ruler of Balkh and Hissar, Amir Joku, as well as the Emir of Iku Timur, Emir Suleiman Shah, Timur's son-in-law, Emir Muayyad of the Orlot clan. As a rule, persons bearing the title of Amir ul-Umar were considered rulers of the border

regions, military and civilian rulers of their subordinate provinces. There were four Beklarbeks on the next level.[2]

Sahibkiran also often repeats that if the emirs, senior officials do not believe in tomorrow, it will undermine the foundations of the state. He stresses that the government and those who deserve domination will have the same trust. Only those who know the basics of the secrets of war, a way to break the enemy's army, who, without losing themselves in the heat of war, can join the battle with open arms, who can quickly fix it if the ranks of the army are broken, deserve an emirate and rule. Amir ul-Umar, who may be his deputy, also pays attention to the qualities and considers worthy of such a high position a man who can command all personnel with glory and beauty, and punish those who oppose him.

The Amirs were divided into amirs of 1-12 ranks, depending on the rank of the heads of 1-12 thousand troops and subordinated to each other from the bottom up. During the war, they were considered the viceroys of Amir ul-Umar. The rank emirs were the leaders of the Navarrese emirs characteristic of Timur, who came from 12 clans that received the stigma. The rest of the amirs came from a clan that did not receive 28 stamps, and were simply called amirs or uluses, amirs of districts. A total of 313 people contested the title. When we approach the power of the emirs, who have power or supremacy, from the point of view of state law, where they were rulers, they were also persons with civil and military powers.

A management apparatus was also formed in the uluses and khokimiyats, these bodies were more involved in tax collection, distribution, court cases and army supplies. During the campaign, the emirs of the uluses and districts had to assemble an army in the amount of one horseman from each tent, one horseman from both tents and one horseman from each settled population. The structure within the army was built according to the decimal system, headed by foremen, centurions, and thousands. During the campaigns, severe punishments were imposed in the troops for those who did not obey the orders of their superiors above themselves.[4]

”The decision of the thousandth was imposed on the centurion, from the centurion to the foreman, and the foreman to his subordinates, and those who did not follow this were punished,” at the army headquarters every eighteen people were chained to a tent. The duties of the leaders, both among the military and among the subjects, consisted in punishing the disobedient, expelling those who did not fulfill their duty, and electing other people in their place. He believed that the power of the leader, whose power was weak from the whip and stick, was not worthy of the position he held, since Amir Timur forbade it because he did not like corporal punishment.

His instructions and thoughts on military law are striking in their correctness and accuracy, as if a necklace is built on a string. According to the order of the Emirates,

one of them was appointed viceroy to another, the first emir was appointed viceroy to the second, thus, to the eleventh - twelfth emir, in turn, the twelfth Amir was considered viceroy to Amir ul-Umar, and he to Sahibkiran. Reading further the compiled order, we see that Amir Temur has shed light on deeper and deeper layers of the essence of the matter. [5]

For example, he forbids entrusting the case of the foreman to the centurion, and the case of the emir to Amir ul-Umar. But whoever of the emirs asks for a job out of curiosity, he will say that he can be assigned a task.

The level of their promotion from the lowest rank to the highest is also quite perfect: if Bahadur (warriors) distinguished themselves in battle, then in the first rank – a foreman, in the next – a centurion, in the third - who received the right to a thousandth. When one of the subordinates of the ten showed bravery, the soldiers assigned primarily with foremen, but who showed themselves in self-defense, were excluded.

In the "Regulations", the system of war crimes and punishments in this regard also found expression in special rules: – if employees run away from the battlefield during the battle, let them deprive us of favor; – if employees retreat forcibly, let them accept our apologies; ; – if employees chop down the enemy with swords and are wounded, let them they read eulogies to him and take note that he is wounded; – whatever service he is in until old age, he should not be deprived of his position or demoted, let them receive useful advice from him.

In this code, we see that for the first time in the history of military law, Amir Timur introduced a military allowance: “if subordinates are captured, let them not be killed, which of the prisoners will come to our shelter, let them trust such a soldier and cherish him, because he, faithful to his master, reserved the right to be eaten salt.” Such judgments and regulations did not arise by themselves, they were all based and formed on the life experience of Amir Temur.[4]

If officials harass a subordinate, that is, it means going beyond the official position, then the official himself is given to the victims. If senior and local chiefs harassed people of lower ranks, then beyond their competence they were entitled to a fine depending on their property. Here, in the first case, officials can be punished until the victim wants to. However, the elders and local chiefs avoided fines for their crimes.[6]

In the second article in the "Regulations", i.e. in the section of military law, it was separately considered on the regulations of the official's maintenance. This can be considered natural, because the preservation of a centralized state in the strict and fair light of military laws was, first of all, a necessity. What aspects are mainly taken into account when maintaining an employee? This has found expression in several "Regulations", including; maintenance of an employee; provision of financial support

(fee) to an employee; distribution of fees to an employee; raising the rank of employees and increasing their suitability; procedures for giving gifts to sons and grandchildren; laws of gift giving and gifts. Amir Timur also puts justice first in creating regulations to retain employees.[3] Preferring that one warrior out of every ten should be called a foreman, when electing a foreman, attention was paid to the fact that he was more experienced, fair, brave and valiant than the other nine warriors, and this was supported by the law.

Conclusion:

Many works and scientific articles have been written about Amir Timur. But the sad fact is that we still do not have thoroughly studied critical comparative analyses of all literature and sources about them. And the very fact that in Central Asia, in Timur's homeland, namely on the territory of the state he created, there are still few deeply analyzed scientific works intended for a wide range of readers. In Timur's writings on issues of state and law, no perfect research has been conducted. Amir Timur was one of the great rulers who left a bright mark in the history of Uzbek statehood, it was through the efforts of this man that the tyranny of the Genghisids, who created political fragmentation, was eliminated in the XIV century. As a result, a centralized state was created on a vast territory from the Chinese wall in the south to India, in the west to the Mediterranean Sea. Thanks to the constitutional document “Regulations”, a fair order and legislation were introduced, where special attention was paid to the protection of human interests and rights.

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